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**ISSUES OF IMPROVING THE MECHANISM OF COLLECTION OF TAX
DEBTS OF LEGAL ENTITIES AND INDIVIDUAL ENTREPRENEURS****Hakimov Ulug'bek Furqat o'g'li**

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Annotation: In this article tax debts of legal entities and individual entrepreneurs were analyzed. Opinions of foreign and domestic scholars about tax debts were studied. In addition, suggestions and recommendations are given about reducing and improving the effective collection of tax arrears

Key words: legal entities, individual entrepreneurs, tax system, taxes and fees, tax debt.

Today, reforms in the country are being implemented not only to support entrepreneurs but also to broadly develop the tax system as well.

The tax system, taxes - are one of the most effective tools in the regulation of the economy by the state. Accordingly, since the first years of independence, our country has undergone many reforms in the field of taxation, as in all areas of the economic infrastructure. The work on this issue is aimed not only at collecting taxes and fees, but also to replenish the state budget by reducing tax arrears.

It is known that the main part of the state budget revenues of the Republic of Uzbekistan is formed by the collection of taxes and fees. Timely and full payment of taxes will serve to timely finance the expenditure part of all measures taken at the state level, including the budget and trust funds.

Further improvement of the economic potential of business entities, creating a mechanism that is acceptable to them in the future and allows the budget to increase revenues from taxes and levies, ensuring investment attractiveness and financial stability of enterprises, Find substantiated proposals to reduce tax arrears due to receivables and payables, which directly affect the increase in revenues from taxes and fees and the development of practical advice and concrete solutions for the development of their activities is one of the current problems.

In this regard, it is important to ensure a timely and complete collection of taxes and fees. Ensuring the timely payment of taxes is done by preventing the occurrence of tax debt as much as possible and its effective collection after its occurrence.

It should be noted that the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan pays special attention to this issue. According to Article 51, “Citizens are obliged to pay taxes and local fees established by law”.¹

Therefore, one of the most important issues for the tax authorities is to reduce the tax arrears of taxpayers and prevent the emergence of new debts, as well as to control the receipt of taxes and levies in the budget on time.

Priorities for improving the financial and tax system of the country, including some issues of tax collection, have been studied by several foreign and local scholars.

Margherita Ebraico (2015), a foreign scholar who has conducted research on the subject, called for the development and promotion of taxes and levies in the country, as well as strict measures against taxpayers with tax arrears. She also emphasizes that it will have a positive effect on reducing tax arrears on taxes and levies and preventing their occurrence in the future.²

In this regard, S.N. Alikhin and D.A. Levacheva (2018) of Russia has conducted research on this topic and talked about the theoretical foundations of the mechanism of tax debt collection. In their research, they noted the complexity of collecting tax arrears from the taxpayer, as well as expanding the tax base, and stressed the importance to develop a mechanism for collecting tax arrears based on the financial condition of businesses with tax arrears.³

In addition, also notes in her research work that increasing the process of seizing property from business entities with existing tax arrears would be effective.

One of our local scientists, commented on the causes of tax arrears and their elimination, saying, “The high tax burden has a number of negative consequences for businesses. Such consequences include the increase in tax arrears, the expansion of the shadow economy, the increase in accounts payable. The tax system should minimize the possibility of legal and illegal tax evasion.

Also, according to the tax arrears are mainly due to the fact that the burden of VAT and property taxes is borne by industrial enterprises, which leads to an uneven distribution of the tax burden and a relatively heavy tax burden on industrial enterprises. This will prevent companies from ending the tax debt problem.

¹ Constitution (2019). Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

² Margherita Ebraico (2015). An Assessment of the Performance of the Italian Tax Debt Collection System. Taxation papers, p-53.

³ S.N. Alikhin, D.A. Levacheva (2018). Evolution of the mechanism for enforced collection of debt to the budget. Taxes, p-28.

At the same time, the ways to avoid tax evasion by introducing a procedure for determining the collection of tax arrears on all other accounts of the business entity in case of full or partial non-fulfillment of the collection order imposed on the main account by the tax authorities within a month. To this end, the development of relevant tax regulations, as well as the introduction of amendments and additions to existing ones, will lead to significant results in improving tax legal literacy of taxpayers, strengthening the payment culture, and eliminating tax arrears by improving the efficiency.

In our opinion, it is important to sharply reduce the collection of tax arrears from businesses in today's pandemic situation, to provide them with tax benefits and privileges, to protect taxpayers and individual entrepreneurs from the crisis, and to avoid unnecessary tax collection costs.

From what we've discussed above, we can draw a conclusion that the reduction of the tax rate in recent years has created a wide range of opportunities for business entities to conduct their activities with ease. Nevertheless, there are examples of businesses not being able to pay the taxes on time. One of the reasons for this issue is the complexity of the process for collecting tax debts in full and in a timely manner.

In our opinion, the following recommendations would be useful to increase the effectiveness of collecting tax arrears in full without any delays:

- to disenfranchise the business owners with tax arrears of the right to use free public schools or hospitals. The reason for this is that the majority of the funds raised by taxes are spent on these government-funded organizations;
- stratification of the penalty rate towards private individuals from the big business entities;
- to use stricter penalties against businesses with tax arrears;
- to use the assistance of the media (radio, tv, or social media) to announce the list of business entities with tax arrears and further educate the general public about our tax system and the penalties for not paying taxes on time.

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6. Data of the State Tax Committee and the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan.